

Depiction of Art as Reflected on Kunal Ceramics

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Abstract

An important feature of Kunal, a pre Harappan site in Haryana, was the use of different ceramics on which various aspects of the culture are depicted. A large variety of patterns can be seen on the pot sherds. The present paper is an attempt to analyze the painted decorative styles on ceramics recovered from Kunal. The paintings demonstrate a remarkable blend of geometrical as well as natural motifs, rendering natural harmony to the subject. The paper is focused upon an overview of the different kinds of patterns or art practices on ceramics recovered from Kunal.

Key Words: Pre Harappan, Ceramics, geometric motif, non-geometric motif, floral or foliage motif

Kunal (29°30'N 75°41'E) is one of the earliest pre-Harappan sites in Haryana, located in the Ratia Tehsil of Fatehabad district in Haryana lies in the flood plain of now dried river bed of mythical Saraswati. The modern town is a part of and lies next to the ancient settlement. The site of Kunal is important since it has provided the evidence of not only the existence of the Pre-harappan culture as it was in its prime time, but also of preceding and succeeding cultures as well. Kunal is the only site included in this category. The old path of the River runs to the north of the site. The study may enable a probe into the various facets of receptiveness of art in a society through the paintings on pottery, a tradition that spans over time and space. Although these constitute a very small proportion of the vast material assemblages, it is of extreme significance in providing a source of information. The paper is based on field data recovered during excavation at the site from 2017-20.

Figure 1 General view of the site

Figure 2 General view of excavated trenches at Kunal

Painted ceramic means beautifying vessel by applying paint on the surface of the ceramic where the expression of the potter/painter's aesthetic sensibilities, and also a reflection of the natural surroundings can be noticed. The aesthetic quality of painted pot is apparently related to the artistic beauty of the patterns executed. These designs and patterns are constituted of motifs and elements, can be classified as geometric, non-geometric, human, floral or foliage motif etc (Rao 1963; Manchanda 1972; Joshi 1972). The presence or absence of certain motifs, its frequency, or continuity and change over time may be used to formulate typological history and chronological framework. The complexity of the painting style is incurred when one looks into their internal variations in patterning the decorations. The cultural and social life of the society can be imagined through the study of the paintings on pottery Basically use of space on any vessel by the potter, as it improves the external appearance making it visually appealing.

The actual habitation deposit exposed so far belongs to the earliest phase of the occupation at the site with pit- or subterranean dwellings of the pre-Harappan people. The ceramic assemblage at the site of Kunal constitutes of a Red ware industry with varied surface treatments ranging from appliqué to incised decorations and a chocolate/black slip on the body. The ceramic industry as a whole closely related to the pre-Harappan Hakra wares to mature Harappa and PGW. The vessels are made of medium fine fabric without any gritty inclusions, though the presence of tempering in the form of fine sand is clearly visible. The clay is mostly well-levigated as it gives a compact feel to the surface and the core of the pots. Most of the vessels are made on medium to first wheel. Some vessels are made on a slow wheel with uneven striation marks in different parts and the use of luting techniques is visible in manufacturing the complete vessel. Handmade vessels are also recovered. In some cases, the rims are wheel-made with perfect striations luted to an uneven body with the finger impressions. The vessels are light-weight, medium to thin bodied, except for storage jars which are heavy and have a thick body. In most cases the pottery has a self-slip with smooth surface, while instances of a light to bright red slip have also been noticed independent of the type of surface treatment being used. Evidence of firing suggests a degree of advanced technique, the undulating surface and limited shapes of the vessels suggest that the industry has not fully evolved when compared to the Mature Harappan period.

One of the most important criteria has been noticed on ceramics i.e., paintings. These paintings are of variety of patterns, constituting of motifs and elements like geometric, non-geometric, human, floral motif etc. Regularity of forms and outstanding symmetry between various component motifs, supplemented by the best rhythmic effect are clearly established by pre-Harappan potters. The paintings demonstrate a remarkable blend of geometrical as well as natural motifs, rendering natural harmony to the subject. The vessels were generally painted before firing, so that in the process of firing the paint adhered to the surface and attained durability. The colour of the paint sometimes varied due to varying temperatures during firing. Some unique forms of art have been noticed in the ceramic assemblages of Kunal. The artists of that time surely had fine artistic sensibilities and a vivid imagination. Their delineation of foliage and animal figures was highly realistic in nature. Aesthetic senses are also visible in ornamental motives. A large quantity of pottery excavated from the site, enable us to understand the gradual evolution of various design motifs as employed in different shapes, and styles.

The painted designs on pottery show various motifs, which may be classified as follows:

- Geometric - Geometric motifs like straight lines, wavy and zigzag lines loops, triangles, squares, circles and dots, diamonds or lozenge pattern, chevron pattern, etc.
- Naturalistic- Flora, Fauna, Human - Naturalistic motifs are the representations of the living world in graphic forms. They include vegetation (floral), birds and animals (faunal), and human motifs.
- Others- Sun symbol, swastika or pipal leaf might be a religious symbol.

Depiction of some sherds and vessel given below- (Courtesy Department of Archaeology & Museums, Haryana)

1. Broken Pot, Red Ware- Alternately filled with crisscross or net within triangle in between thick lines (Geometric Pattern)
2. Rim of Handi, Red Ware- Loops with low curve with thick lines and bands on rim (Geometric Pattern)
3. Rim of Handi, Red Ware- Thick horizontal line (Geometric Pattern)
4. Broken Miniature pot, Red Ware- Vertical lines from horizontal thick line. (Geometric Pattern)

Broken painted pot. Red Ware, Esthetic sense of artist highly noticeable. Depiction of a pipal leaf with human eyes, upper portion of the leaf is filled with crisscross or net designs. It is an impeccably beautiful design. The neck portion also painted with thick black band. It might be a religious symbol.

<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Rim of Handi, Red Ware- Diamond pattern filled with criss-cross or net design with two horizontal lines (Geometric Pattern)2. Rim of bowl, Red Ware, Biochrome, horizontal and wavy lines (Geometric Pattern)3. Sherd of Bowl, Red Ware, Biochrome, Geometric Floral Patterns with horizontal lines (Blend of Geometric and Naturalistic pattern)4. Sherd, Red Ware- Diamond pattern filled with criss-cross or net design with two horizontal lines as borders drawn horizontally. (Geometric Pattern)5. Rim of pot, Red Ware- Diamond pattern filled with criss-cross or net design with a horizontal line as borders drawn horizontally. Above this there are two more horizontal lines (Geometric Pattern)6. Rim, Red Ware- Loops with low curve radiating from with horizontal line below another row (three) of horizontal lines. (Geometric Pattern)	
<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Sherd of a vase, Red slipped red ware with black painted foliage motives on body (Naturalistic pattern)2. Broken lid, red ware with horizontal lines and loops with low curve (Geometric Pattern)	

<p>Broken pot, Red ware, Biochrome, horizontal lines (Geometric Pattern)</p>	
<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Sherd of vessel, Red slipped red ware, fish-scale designs within horizontal lines. A thick band covering neck and rim (Blend of Geometric and Naturalistic pattern)2. Sherd of a vase, Micasious red ware. Horizontal lines on body (Geometric pattern)3. Part of a handled jar, Red ware, made on slow wheel, incised rows of wavy lines (chevron pattern) but in crude form. Horizontal lines on handle and thick band on neck (Geometric pattern)4. Part of a jar, Bichrome red ware, multiple rows of chevron patterns in between black lines, a thick white band on shoulder and thick lines on neck and rim (Geometric pattern)	

<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Broken Miniature Bowl, Red Ware. Rows of vertical lines and Cross radiating from thick lines. (Geometric pattern)2. Broken Miniature Bowl, Red Ware. Rows of vertical lines. Below there is a thick band(Geometric pattern)3. Sherd of a bowl, Red ware. Oblique lines above black band(Geometric pattern)4. Broken miniature pot, Chocolate slipped red ware. Loops with low curve radiating from edge of the rim (Geometric pattern)5. Broken Miniature Bowl, Red Ware. Rows of vertical lines from black band rest on a thick line. (Geometric pattern)	
<p>Broken bowl, Red Ware. Decorated with a Horizontal Band of Circular Motifs in between two thick bands (Geometric pattern)</p>	
<p>Sherd, Red slipped red ware, Depiction of wild Bore (Naturalistic pattern- fauna)</p>	

<p>Sherd, Red ware, Depiction of buffalo. (Naturalistic pattern- fauna)</p>	
<p>Two different Sherds, Red ware, Depiction of cattle (Naturalistic pattern- funa)</p>	

<p>Broken pot, Red ware, Black painting on red surface. Diamond motif filled with crisscross or net in between multiple horizontal lines. (Geometric Pattern)</p>	
<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Rim of Handi, Red Ware, Loops with low curve with multiple horizontal lines and bands on neck (Geometric Pattern)2. Sherd, Red ware, Biochrome, Depiction of a pipal leaf below thick horizontal band (Blend of Geometric and Naturalistic- flora)	
<p>Sherd, Red ware, Depiction of snail (Naturalistic pattern- fauna)</p>	

1. Sherd, Red slipped red ware, fish-scale designs within horizontal lines. (Geometric pattern)
2. Sherd, Red ware, Bichrome, wavy line on thick band. (Geometric pattern)
3. Sherd, Red ware, Bichrome, crisscross oblique lines with thick bands. (Geometric pattern)
4. Sherd, Red ware, Bichrome, Horn motif (Religious symbol)
5. Sherd, Chocolate slipped Red ware, Graffiti with sun motif. (Religious symbol)
6. Sherd, Red ware, linear composition (Geometric pattern)
7. Sherd, Red ware, Bichrome, linear composition (Geometric pattern)
8. Sherd, Red ware, Bichrome, Horn motif (Religious symbol)

The painted decorations are a reflection of the excellent artistic skill of the artisans, their acceptance, and involvement in the social and cultural life of the society. The artists depicting the designs had a very clear sense of utilizing the available space; sometimes restricting himself by drawing panels or registers, and sometimes depended on the shape and size of the vessel. The paintings demonstrate a remarkable blend of geometrical as well as natural motifs, rendering natural harmony to the subject.

In the above discussion it is attempted to classify the diverse patterns seen on ceramics recovered from Kunal. They often used only a fix set of patterns. It is suggested that some of these creations are not random scribbles but involve a certain understanding of the culture itself. Above examples show their craftsmanship was remarkable and practically demonstrate the imaginary limit of human capabilities in creating such designs.

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